

UZBEKISTAN TESTICLE

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Abstract: *Anatomic structure and topographical location of the testis. Their histological structure, as well as physiological processes. Mechanical, physical, and chemical disorders of the function of the connector. Which countries are most likely to have sexually abnormalities. Different diseases in the testicles and treatment mechanisms.*

Keywords: *Testis, Testis, Spermatozoon, Seed, Sex, Hormone.*

INTRODUCTION

The content of the article: testis (testis, Greek - orchis) is one of the dual organs in the human body. This hormone is important for the formation of secondary sex symbols in boys. These properties of the testicle cause the inclusion of ulcers in the gland. The testis hangs in the germ of the sperm. The sperm transmits the seed path, blood, blood vessels, nerves, and muscle fibers. The testis is separated by a barrier between each other. The horn is very well protected from the outside, it is surrounded by 7 layers of crust. It has an oval shape and is slightly flattened on both sides. distinguishable edges. This is explained by the fact that the edges are located on the back of the edges, and the thickness of the retina lies in the excess of the testis. The human body is 0.7% of the total body weight. The testis is covered by a whitish veil (tunica albuginea) with a testicular parenchyma (parenchyma testis) at the bottom. The back of the testis enters the tissues that attach to the testicular pharynx from the inside, forming the testicular devoir range. In these pieces there are 3-4 burrowing seed tubes (tubulin seminiferous contorti), which produce hypermethystoids. These tubes perform important functions and functions. They are joined to one another and form the right seed tubes. The right testicular tubes (mediastinum testis) are inserted directly into one another. There are 11-14 testicular drainage tubes in the testis and move to the back of the testis.

The testis has separate cells that act as a secretion. They produce various hormones and fluids. Sertoli cells in the testis secrete the hormones called phagocytosis and igniting, which provide nutrition for the sperm. In addition, Leydig cells, together with testosterone, which is a male hormone, secrete an

estradiol hormone that acts as an estrogen. These cells are regulated by the pituitary gland.

Scabies: The testis (epididymis) is located on the back of the testis. It is anatomically divided into 3 parts:

1. Head (caput epididymis)
2. Body (corpus epididymis)
3. Tail (cauda epididymis)

The testicular tubes form 12–15 testicular segments in the form of a conis, separated by a thin film at the beginning of the torsion testicle. .The anterior testicular tubes form numerous curvature and move in the direction of the tail.

This tube becomes the seed-bearing testicle in the tail of the testis. Male sex cells (spermatozoa) are formed only in the twist of the testis. The remaining tubes of the testis and testicles are the seed-bearing tubes. The embryonic development of the testis develops in conjunction with the urinary system. The testis develops slowly as it moves slowly across the fourth lumbar vertebra. When the testis reaches the 5th lumbar vertebrae, the urinary tract is separated from the urinary system and directed downwards. When the fetus is three months old, it stops near the anus and is there for a long time. By the age of 7 months, testicles begin to enter the canal. The baby is in bed before birth or at birth. During this time, the testis is formed. In some cases, the testicle can be left in the abdomen or in the anterior duct without getting into the bowel, resulting in birth defects. If the mop yak does not fall on one side, then the monarchism, if not on both sides, will cause diseases called cryptorchism. The cause of the congenital aneurysm is the obstruction of the peritoneal cavity. Because testis is an important part of the male genitalia, it has led to numerous investigations. Another characteristic of the testis is that the temperature in it is 2 - 3 degrees below the body temperature. This indicator is important for germination. It is also harmful to wear long diapers for young boys. Tight teenagers wear tight shirts as they cause the ostrich to cling. This causes the testis to approach the body temperature and impair its function. The fact that chefs are constantly working at high temperatures can cause different sexual weaknesses. When given attention, the testicles are located close to the body on cold days, and on hot days, on the contrary, away from the body. This property of the testicle regulates its temperature. Now we will examine some diseases of the testicle. Cryptorchism: The name of the disease is of the Greek origin, meaning "hidden testicle". The testis is not out of the ordinary, but on the outside. Pathology of the fetus chromosomes, hormonal defects in the mother and fetus, defect of the duct and other factors cause the testis to fall out of the cavity. As you know, in the 9th month of pregnancy, the testicles are completely sore. The birth of a testicle at birth is one of the most important signs of a child's health. Parents need to be

vigilant, and if the testicle has not been in bed for 6 months, I have to take it to the doctor immediately. Typically, children who are 2-3 years of age are treated with medication. Aging catalysts are recovered through opiate. The longer the delay, the more severe the consequences. There are many kinds of crypto currency. In a fake cryptorchism, testicles are often found on the bed and can be treated without surgery. If a child is diagnosed with genuine crypto currency, it is necessary to provide timely treatment or surgery, as mentioned above. Children do not have to worry about the disease because of the pain. It is important to feel the body for inspection, and to undergo ultrasound to be more sure. Orchitis: This is a testicular disease, and is a complication of many diseases. These are infectious diseases such as parotitis, influenza, sore throat and typhus. In addition to these diseases, it can be caused by damage to the walnut. Sharp orchid pain in the testis causes sudden pain, redness and tension in the affected side, and fever. The temperature may rise to 38-39 degrees, and the patient may experience severe tremor. The disease may increase the size of the testis, but the size of the testis remains unchanged. In this case, the more the patient moves, the greater the pain. This can be caused by the pain in the thigh and the pain in the thigh. With the beginning of pus in the orchid, the skin becomes red, causing some softened areas in the testis.

CONCLUSION

This can lead to worse consequences. In the course of the disease, non-recurrence can turn into a chronic type. This can lead to complications such as infertility, epididymitis, testicular atrophy. Every organ in the body is the most important to him. Therefore, we must take care of every organ and perfect it.

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